

THE EFFICIENCY OF APPLYING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF PLANTS

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Abstract: *For farmers working in the field of agriculture, monitoring the development of agricultural products in greenhouses and other closed areas, automatic irrigation, fertilizing, determination of parameters of soil composition and based on them automatic management system software and technology designed for the cultivation of each agricultural product has been developed.*

Methods of climate control, temperature, humidity, nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus level measuring devices, provision of nutrients, fruit ripening and irrigation devices were used.

Key words: *agricultural crops, clusters, monitoring hardware and software, sensors, smart greenhouse, monitoring system, web site, web applications, database, management system.*

In modern life, the rapid development of all spheres of society and state life requires the implementation of reforms based on modern innovative ideas, developments and technologies that ensure rapid and high-quality development of our country on the way to becoming one of the leaders of world civilization. Therefore, significant results are being achieved in the fundamental reform of agriculture as well as in all aspects of our economy, introduction of market mechanisms in the sector, further improvement of the product processing system and formation of added value.

The rapid development of modern information and communication technologies is the reason for the wide-scale development of all industries in our country, which, in turn, creates the possibility of carrying out this work through the types and directions.

An example of this is modern services that are rapidly developing, i.e. efficient use of land plots by farms, production of agricultural products along the edges of fields, irrigation and collector-drainage networks, as well as the use of lightweight, low-cost equipment and sensors, their remote control, automatic Determining the composition of the soil without excessive labor and creating an automatic irrigation system will make our daily life easier and more convenient. As a result of extensive agricultural reforms in recent years, the attitude of farms to land use, especially to the edges of fields, along irrigation and collector-drainage networks, has changed. By increasing the production of agricultural products in these lands, significant positive results will be achieved in terms of obtaining additional income and meeting the needs of their employees for food products.

The formation and development of the theory of innovation, the Austrian scientist Y. Schumpeter made a great contribution. In the 1930s, Y. The concept of innovation was introduced by Schumpeter, and it meant possible changes due to the application of new or improved technical, technological, organizational decisions in the processes of production, sale, and delivery of products. Also, from the point of view of changes, innovations include La Perre, Yu. Yakovets, F. Valenta, L. Voldachkova and others define it as "innovation - any change that occurs in the internal structure of the economy by moving from the initial state to a new state" or "the development of a creative idea and its transformation into a finished product, process or system." E. Mansfeld, B. Innovation is interpreted as a process by Santo, B. Twiss and other foreign scientists, and it is defined as a social-technical-economic process that leads to the creation of the best products and

technologies according to their characteristics through the practical use of ideas and inventions. It should be emphasized that the factors explaining the economic content of ideas and discoveries and their sources are not indicated in these definitions, which led to a more unclear definition of the concept of innovation. Scientist N.D. Kondratev, who founded the theory of big cycles with a duration of 50-60 years, developed models of business cycles, made a great contribution to the implementation of innovations. He proved that the transition to a new cycle is related to the expansion of the stock of capital goods, which makes it possible to create conditions for the introduction of accumulated inventions. N.D. Kondratev connected the transition to a new cycle with the development of technology: "Before the beginning of the rising wave of each big cycle, and sometimes with its beginning, considerable changes are observed in the conditions of the economic life of the society. These changes are usually manifested in one or another combination, in technical inventions and discoveries, in profound changes in the techniques of production and exchange. According to N.D. Kondratev, science and technology innovations play an important role in changes in the economic life of society. Taking into account the need to ensure the economic efficiency of innovations, a number of Russian economists viewed innovation as "a new product or service, a production method, an innovation in organizational, financial, research and other fields that provides cost savings or the creation of conditions for such savings." In the studies of economists of our country, the term "innovation" began to be widely used in connection with the transition to market relations. A number of economists, including A.A. Abdug'aniev, A.V. Vahobov, A.M. Kadirov, S.S. Gulomov, Yo.A. Abdullaev, Ch. Murodov, T.Kh. Farmonov, O'.P.Umurzakov, N.S.Khushmatov, A.Mukhtorov and others have carried out important scientific researches. Thus, summarizing the definitions given above, the concept of innovation can be defined as follows. Innovation is the introduction of a new or significantly improved product (goods, service) or process, a new method of marketing, a new organizational method in the organization of workplaces or external relations.

One of the main goals of the project is to develop a technology for remote control of farm plots on closed land and a remote control system for the cultivation of agricultural products.

Indoor air temperature, air humidity, Ph content of the air, soil temperature, chemical composition of the soil and soil composition of the indoor areas are determined using detectors and transmitted to the sensors every minute. The readings are displayed on the sensor monitor.

Modern 5th generation greenhouses are considered to be a whole complex: air humidity, climate control, automation of drip irrigation, automatic opening and closing of doors and slots, creating favorable conditions for plant growth and development.

The created technology can be used for optional agricultural crops. The priority aspects of technology from the automation system of 5th generation greenhouses are that plant growth and development, the plant's demand for which fertilizer are controlled based on the automated system, all performed tasks: drip irrigation, door and window opening and closing, climate control, determining the ripeness of the crop. enters into the main task and is under control.

In advanced agricultural systems, various "smart technologies" (smart-sensors) are installed based on crop and environmental conditions. For example, climate control - measuring tools for temperature, humidity, nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus levels, nutrient supply, fruit ripening and irrigation devices are included. Their use guarantees an increase in productivity of at least 30 percent. In addition, improved systems will be introduced in the production and marketing chains of agricultural products, and eventually the possibility of collecting large amounts of electronic data will be created. As a result of their storage and analysis, it is possible to effectively use water, land and other limited resources, and ensure the quality and safety of food.

The created technology receives real-time centralized information on the growth of agricultural products, irrigation, soil parameters, fertilizer requirements, drip irrigation control and remote monitoring of fruit ripening through a mobile communication application, and based on an intelligent system, sensors and sensors can not only grow crops, but also fully control the harvest. It also helps to save. In advanced agricultural systems, various "smart technologies" (smart-sensors) are installed based on a single goal based on crop and environmental conditions. For example, early detection of pests and diseases, climate control - measuring devices for temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide level, nutrient supply and irrigation devices are included. Their use guarantees an increase in productivity of at least 30 percent. In addition, improved systems will be introduced in the production and marketing chains of agricultural products, and eventually the possibility of collecting large amounts of electronic data will be created. The introduction of the system will increase the possibility of export of agricultural products, the control system "from production to the counter" will achieve up to 50% of production. Labor productivity will increase by 30 percent, necessary practical skills will be acquired for full crop production. Conditions are created for the creation of varieties of crops resistant to stresses, high yield, adapted to transport, rich in bioactive substances.

The use of satellite data and remote sensing technologies will also be tested for rapid and accurate assessment of the condition of agricultural lands and the crops grown on them. With this, all types of agricultural crops are cultivated and land evaluation is achieved throughout the republic. Satellite data will serve to form an information-analytical base on "precision farming" in the republic, and an opportunity will be created for farms to use automated systems.

In conclusion, the above technology, developed over many years of study and research, has the ability to modify the software for additional modules depending on the needs and wishes of the farm. The created device can be used for optional agricultural crops. The growth and development of the plant, which fertilizer the plant needs are controlled under an automated system, all the performed tasks: drip irrigation, climate control, determination of the ripeness of the crop are included in the function of the created device and will be under its control. In the cultivation of agricultural products, the main focus is on the amount of fertilizer. This technology uses sensors and software to monitor the soil composition at a distance of 2m² around the plant. Plant condition monitoring through the website is stored in the database and can be monitored and controlled remotely through the mobile application. Desktop - C++ (Cross Platform) uses less resources, so the Arduino part of the project complex being created is written in the S++ programming language, and the mobile application is written in the Java programming language. The created technology was introduced to Jizzakh, Bukhara, and Tashkent regions. As the technology is convenient in all aspects, it is recommended to use it for all types of land areas of Uzbekistan.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Abasxanova, X. Yu, and U. B. Amirsaidov. "Microprocessors. A textbook for higher education. Toshkent-2016." b 280: 26-091.
2. Abasxanova, X. Yu. "Textbook for college students majoring in" digital technology" 5.55. 01.01-" Telecommunication technologies" Tashkent." (2021).
3. Abaskhanova, X. Yu, and I. N. Juraev. "Khoshimova FR Textbook for college students majoring in" digital technology" 5.55. 01.01-" Telecommunication technologies". Tashkent." (2021).

4. Abaskhanova, H. Yu, and K. Sherjanova. "Creating microprocessor systems for people with disabilities creating microprocessor systems for people with disabilities. Collection of reports of the republican scientific-practical conference" prospects for the development of information and communication technologies." Karshi-2018." 87-89.
5. Abaskhanova, H. Y. "Applying infocommunication technologies to agriculture." Current problems of modern science. Xalqaro konferentsiya. Chicago USA-2022.-6.
6. Abasxanova, X. Yu. "Modeling digital devices with the help of vhdl programming language. Current problems of modern science." International conference. Chicago USA. 2022.
7. Markhamat Y. Khaydarova, & Khalima Y. Abaskhanova. (2022). Applying infocommunication technologies to agriculture. International scientific and current research conferences, 1(01), 27–29. Retrieved from <https://orientalpublication.com/index.php/iscrc/article/view/615>
8. Yu, Abaskhanova Kh. "Analysis of information and communication technologies in green environment monitoring." International conference on information science and communications technologies applications, trends and opportunities: ICISCT. 2022.
9. Yu, Abaskhanova KH. "Features of introduction of innovative technologies in agriculture of Uzbekistan." International scientific journal "Universum: Technical science (2021).
10. Yu, Abaskhanova Kh. "Advantages of using digital technologies in agriculture." Agro science. Agrarian-economic, scientific-practical magazine. Tashkent-2022.3-appendix (81)-no.-pages104-105.